

A Graduate Tracer Study of Latian Elementary School SY 2008-2012: Basis for a Proposed Intervention Program

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Abstract. The purpose of the study was to trace the graduate of batch 2008-2012 of Latian Elementary School basis for an intervention program. The researcher made use of the cross-sectional research design. The respondents of the study were the 247 graduate pupils' of Latian Elementary School. The study revealed that most of the graduates were male, had seven years of schooling, Blaen, and had a low monthly family income of P 5,000-10,000. Most of the graduates from 2008-2012 graduated to secondary, increasing from half to one-third of the total number of students. Furthermore, the common reason why they did not move and graduate to secondary was the low income of the family, responsibilities at home, cannot support education in secondary, and the distance from home to school.

Keywords:- Graduate tracer, elementary school, intervention program, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Philippine education has recognized the importance of the achievement of inclusive growth and poverty reduction. Reducing inequalities in school participation and completion can improve the opportunity of each citizen to participate in the processes for socioeconomic development and progress. It is a fundamental right of the citizens, particularly the children, to primary education. However, the government's efforts to achieve the millennium development goals target declined. Recent research in the Philippines Midterm Progress Report assessed that the probability of achieving universal primary education in the country is low based on the net enrollment rate, cohort survival, and completion rate. Similarly, the 2019 EFA Global Monitoring Report identified the Philippines as an enrollment rate that declined from recent years and the lowest number of out-of-school children (Albert, 2016; David & Albert 2015; UNESCO, 2018).

Education is a legal right of a child. Going through compulsory primary education comes with no cost. No Child Left Behind act has been mandated worldwide, which implies that everyone has to undergo education across the globe. Literacy among children develops the lifelong skills essential for life. Elementary education provides meaningful academic learning and socialization skills to prepare children for the complex knowledge, skills, and behaviors they need to move to higher learning and become functional adults in the community. Moreover, the tracer study can

provide the necessary findings to contribute to a school intervention plan of addressing issues on attending and completing the primary education prescribed by the DepEd. As well as provide technical assistance to alleviate the economic status of the populace in the community (Care Kim Vista & Anderson 2018; Dorn, Fuchs & Fuchs 2016; Jacobi, 2018; Obando & Shisanya 2018).

Since Latian Elementary School situate in a poor community in Alabel, there are several reasons for continuing education despite being free. Recommend future action steps, must conduct a Latian Elementary School graduates' tracer to establish a baseline on common causes for not completing education. Several Oplan Balik Eskwela and similar programs operate in the school community, but there are still cases of dropouts and out-of-school youth.

A. Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to trace the graduates from batch 2008-2012 of Latian Elementary School as Basis for a proposed School Intervention Program.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

- What is the Profile of the graduates from 2008-2012 of Latian Elementary School in reference to:
 - Gender;
 - Number of years in schooling;
 - Ethnicity;
 - Education of parents;
 - Size of the family; and
 - Income of the family?
- What is the percentage of graduates from 2008-2012 who graduated secondary education?
- What are the reasons for students not proceeding to graduate from secondary education?
- What intervention program could be formulated out of the result of the study?

B. Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on two theories that helped the researcher guides career development theories to better understand the respondents' life, career, and education choices; the theories were Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Frank Parsons' Trait and Factor Theory.

- a) Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory
Social cognitive theory, by Albert Bandura (1986) cited by Usher & Schunk (2018), was the idea that an individual's motives and behavior construct their

experience. These experiences can break into main categories: influenced by self-efficacy or belief which means that people were influenced by what they see like when others succeed, they also do the same. The actions and factors around them influence an individual that they cannot control. Social cognitive theory helps explain how individuals can set up their career development plans for career development success. They succeed in their career goals through a positive view of their abilities and by surrounding themselves with a positive network of mentors. The framework for this theory is called Bandura's Triadic Reciprocal Model of Casualty. This model says based on a person's output on a mixture of personal characteristics, behaviors, and actions they see from other people and outside factors.

b) Frank Parsons' Trait and Factor Theory

On the other hand, the second theory that was anchored in this study was Frank Parsons' Trait and Factor Theory, this theory entailed three actions. First, the researcher needs to examine the personality traits of the respondents whose career study. Second, there is a need to do an inventory of the character traits. Third, measuring the individual's personality traits against the job characteristics is also a must (Jordan 2019).

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study used a Descriptive cross-sectional survey utilizing data availability, particularly in Latian Elementary School, Municipality of Alabel, Province of Sarangani. It described and interpreted the data accurately and adequately. According to Grotkiewicz & Kowalczyk (2015), a research design accurately depicts the participants. It also represented people who take part in the study or discussion with a particular specific topic. This research design was appropriate because the researcher traced the batch 2008-2012 graduates of Latian Elementary School to formulate the School Intervention Program. The cross-sectional survey was used in this research was further than simply providing information on the frequency of the attributes. This method collected data across the different graduate batches of 2008-2012 public schools in the Municipality of Alabel, Sarangani Province. Hence, this research design was deemed appropriate in this study.

The respondents of the study were the 247 graduate pupils of batch 2008-2012. Census or total enumeration was used. This means that all of the population were included as the study's respondents. Crewell (2016) supported this idea stated that if all members of the whole population were measured, total enumeration would be applied.

The instrument used in the study was based on the Learning Information System (LIS) survey form from the Department of Education. It determined the profile of the students in the public schools that contains the respondents' gender, ethnicity, education of parent, size of the family, the family's income, and the significant difference when

analyzing according to the profile. The number of graduates for batch 2008-2012 who proceed to secondary and the total number of learners who graduated in secondary (DepEd portals, 2020).

The researcher gathered the necessary survey data from the schools they graduated in secondary, particularly in Alegria National High School and Tokawal National High School. The researcher collected other informative data by asking the family members of the respondents because the majority were residing within the community area, and it was straightforward to get the information; proper health protocols observed due to the pandemic. The statistical tools that used in the study were the frequency counts and percentages in sub problems 1 to 4.

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the graduates of Latian Elementary School during the SY:2008-2012. The researcher used frequency counts and percentages in interpreting these data.

A. Graduates of Latian Elementary School from 2008-2012 in terms of Gender

The data on Gender shows that in 2007-2008, 26 out of 48 or 54 percent were female, 22 out of 48 or 46 percent were male. It can be seen that the majority of graduates in Latian Elementary School were female. Moreover, in the calendar year 2008-2009, it could be noted that 23 out of 52 or 44 percent were female, whereas 56 percent or 29 out of 52 were male. In 2009-2010, 23 out of 50 or 46 percent were female while 27 out of 50 or 54 percent were male. Additionally, in 2010-2011, 25 out of 49 or 51 percent were male, and 24 out of 49 or 49 percent were female. Lastly, in 2011-2012, 23 out of 48 or 48 percent were female, and 25 out of 48 or 52 percent were male. In general, most of the graduates of Latian elementary school during the school year 2008-2012 were male. Male appears to be more interested in finishing elementary schooling.

A positive attitude to schools was strongly related to having a father and mother support. Coming from lower socioeconomic family background, being male, and having scientific peers hinder finishing their studies (Breakwell and Beardsell, 2015; Le, Tran, Trinh Nguyen, Nguyen, Vuong, Vu, Bui, Vuong, Vuong Hoang and Nguyen, 2019). Moreover, research shows organic differences in the living brains of boys and girls that may cause them to think and learn differently. Teaching girls and boys in separate classrooms have suggested increasing achievement for both genders. It was one of the options to give a better way of education to children, and it was an excellent opportunity for the student to learn more and explore the world around them (Gurian & Stevens, 2005; Sax, 2005; Lembo, 2015).

B. Graduates of Latian Elementary School from 2008-2012 in terms of Years in Schooling

The data shows that in 2007-2008, 45 out of 48 or 94 percent spent six years in education, 3 out of 48 or 6 percent seven years, and zero in 8 years and above. The data shows that most graduates from Latian Elementary School had spent six years in 2008-2009. We could also see that no

pupils rendered eight years and above in schooling from 2007-2008. While, in the school year 2008-2009, it could be noted that 49 out of 52 or 94 percent spent their schooling within six years, whereas 3 out of 52 or 7 percent spent seven years in education. In 2009 majority of the graduates of Latian Elementary School spent six years in the school year 2008-2009. In 2009-2010, it could glean that 96 percent or 48 out of 50 spent six years in school, while the remaining 2 or 4 percent of pupils spent seven years in schooling. In this year the majority of pupils spent their education in 6 years. Moreover, during the school year 2010-2011, it is traced up that 47 or 96 percent spent within six years in school and 2 or 4 percent spent their schools in 7 years. Data revealed that the majority of the pupils of Latian Elementary School spent school in 6 years. We could see from 2011-2012, and it could have spent 100 percent or 48 pupils their schooling in 6 years. Generally, if we are going to trace up the years spent by the pupils of Latian Elementary School based on the years spent in schooling for the school year 2008-2012, the majority of them spent six years.

The study understands what led these students to enroll in charter schools and why they chose to leave. More specifically, family members significantly impacted students' decisions to employ choice to enroll in charters. Lack of extra-curricular activities in alliances had a substantially negative impact on students' experiences. Educational quality was the foremost characteristic in the determination to transfer out of a charter school.) research afforded a rare look at one particular unique education student's lived experience of dropping out of high school (Hansen, 2010; Neely & Vaquera 2017; Yoder (2017). Likewise, learners acquire the literacy and lifelong skills necessary to get a good job, decent earnings, and access to quality learning opportunities. Countries that successfully end their population with literacy and lifelong skills are usually more significant to meet the economic demands. A highly literate people will be better able to deal with governance issues in a highly diverse society (Hammond, 2015; Hanemann, 2015; Lopes & McKay 2020; Schomburg 2016).

C. Graduates of Latian Elementary School from 2008-2012 in terms of Ethnicity

We could see from the data of Latian Elementary School pupils based on their Ethnicity that in the school year 2007-2008, 36 out of 48 or 75 percent were B'laan, 11 out of 48 or 23 percent were in the Cebuano group, and 1 out of 48 or 2 percent were Muslim. As we could glean from the data, most of the respondents in the school year 2007-2008 were B'laan. Moreover, from 2008-2009, it could note that 33 out of 52 or 63 percent were B'laan, 19 out of 52 or 36 percent were Cebuano. We could see in the data that the majority of the pupils were B'laan. However, there is no Muslim group participant belongs at this year. Furthermore, in 2009-2010, 29 out of 50 or 58 percent were B'laan, 20 out of 50 or 40 percent were Cebuano, and 1 out of 50 or 2 percent were Muslim. We could find that most of the ethnic groups in Latian Elementary School in 2009-2010 mainly were B'laan. In 2010-2011, we could see that 31 out of 49 or 63 percent were B'laan, while 18 out of 49 or 36 percent

belonged to Cebuano. The majority of Latian E/S pupils in the calendar year 2011 were B'laan. Somehow, from 2011-2012, it could note that 30 out of 48 or 62 percent were B'laan, 16 out of 48 or 33 percent corresponded to the group of Cebuano. And the remaining 2 out of 48 or 4 percent of the group were Muslims. The majority of the group is B'laan. In general, if we're going to trace up the graduates of Latian Elementary School during the school year 2008-2012 based on Ethnicity, the majority of them were B'laan.

In the ethnic group in 2010, indigenous people in Mindanao got 12-15 percent of the total population, increasing over the years around. Opportunity deprivation was also found to be strongly correlated with Ethnicity, region, and family background. Ethnicity is an immediate sense of belonging to an ethnolinguistic group. Consanguine because the ties are reckoned with by blood and traced through the family tree. Ethnic grouping in the Philippines denotes genealogical, paternal, and maternal lineage to any of the country's group of the native population (Hassan, Zafrualam, Bahri, Yaapar, Bustami & Alwi 2021; Parangan & Buslon 2020).

D. Graduates of Latian Elementary School from 2008-2012 in terms of Education of Parents

Based on 2007-2008 for elementary, 33 out of 48 or 69 percent have undergraduate parents, 8 out of 48 or 16 percent have graduated. In High school, 4 out of 48 or 8 percent belongs to undergraduate, and graduate from secondary having two students out of 48 or 4 percent. In undergraduate college, the parent shows that 1 out of 48 or 2 percent. As shown, most of the respondents in the school year 2007-2008 have parents who are elementary undergraduates. During 2008-2009, it could note that 34 out of 52 or 65 percent have undergraduates, 9 out of 52 or 17 percent are graduate parents. Whereas 6 out of 52 or 11 percent of whose parents are undergraduate, 2 out of 52 or 5 percent graduate from high school. 1 out of 52 parents or 2 percent is an undergraduate college parent and no result of parents where finish their college. The majority of the participant's parent education was elementary undergraduates in the calendar year 2009. We could look at the table that in the school year 2009-2010, it could be found that 24 out of 50 or 48 percent parents who are elementary undergraduate, 18 out of 50 or 36 percent parents who are graduate from elementary. In high school, undergraduate parents revealed that 5 out of 50 or 10 percent are graduates, and 3 out of 6 percent. However, there is no result of undergraduate or graduate parents in college in the calendar year 2010. The majority of the education of parents was an elementary undergraduate. For the calendar year 2010-2011, it could glean that 25 out of 49 or 51 percent of parents were elementary undergraduates, 16 out of 49 or 32 percent are graduate from elementary. In high school, it shows that 5 out of 49 or 10 percent of parents took undergraduate and 3 out of 49 were graduated from secondary. At the same time, there is no result from student parents that take college in the calendar year 2011. In the school year 2011-2012, it could trace that the education of the parents of respondents reveals that 20 out of 48 or 42 percent were elementary undergraduates, and 15 out of 48 were graduates of elementary. Meanwhile, in high school, it revealed that 5 out

of 48 parents are high school undergraduates. Moreover, there is 1 out of 48 or 2 percent are graduates. Generally, most of the graduates of Latian Elementary School in terms of parents' education during the school year 2008-2012, are undergraduate of elementary level. A study explored how parents' education and literacy skills affect their children's primary education within the context of cultural capital theory. The study shows that most parents were aware of the welfare of education. Still, the reality of their lives, including education and literacy challenges, affected involvement in their children's primary education. Despite this handicap, most parents depend on extended families and community members for assistance. Thus, when parents long to see their wards through formal education, their illiterate status does not become a handicap (Ghanney, 2018; Appiah, Owusu, Yeboah & Ansah 2021; Mesiaislehto, Katsui&Sambaiga 2021).

E. Graduates of Latian Elementary School from 2008-2012 in terms of Size of the Family

The data show that in the 2007-2008 school year, 2 out of 48 or 4 percent were in small families, 45 out of 48 or 94 percent were in the medium-size family, and 1 out of 48 or 2 percent were large families the family. Moreover, in the school year 2008-2009, it could note that 1 out of 52 or 2 percent group belongs to small size family, 49 out of 52 or 92 percent were in the medium size family. School year 2009-2010 and 2010-2011 shows no result from the small and large family graduates. However, in the school year 2009-2010, 50 or 100 percent were in the medium-size family, and in the school year 2010-2011, 49 or 100 percent were in the medium size family. From 2011-2012 graduates in Latian E/S, 1 out of 48 or 2 percent was in small size family, 46 out of 48 or 96 percent were in the medium-size family, and 1 out of 48 or 2 percent were in the large family. Generally, the data shows that Latian Elementary School graduates school year 2008-2012, majority of the participants were in the medium size family.

In addition, the size of the family defines the number of people in the family. The family size in which the child grows, especially if the family does not have adequate resources, affects the child's growth and development due to a lack of quality feeding. Moreover, the predictive role of family economic hardships on student engagement, particularly in the sub-Saharan African context. The study used data from junior high school students in Ghana to examine the association between perceived family economic hardship and students' classroom engagement and the intervening role of future intentions (Ansong, Okumu, Halilton, Chowa, and Eisensmith 2017).

Furthermore, parent educational involvement is an essential avenue for enhancing student outcomes. Moreover, this model extends current parent involvement frameworks by coordinating systematic family engagement in education (Garbacz, McIntosh, Eagle, Dowd-Eagle, Hirano, & Ruppert 2015).

F. Graduates of Latian Elementary School from 2008-2012 in terms of Monthly Income of the Family

The data that that from 2007-2008 the monthly income of family we could notice that 4 out of 48 or 8 percent have monthly income of below P 5000. 42 out of 48 or 88 percent have a monthly payment of P 5,001 to P 10,000, while 1 out of 48 or 2 percent of the graduates of Latian elementary school have parents earning P 10,001 to P 20,000. And 1 out of 48 or 2 percent were the participant's parent with a monthly income of P 20,001 up. We could glean from the data, majority of the respondents in the school year 2007-2008 have parents earning low income from P 5,001 to 10,000. Furthermore, in the calendar year 2009, it could note that --6 out of 52 or 12 percent have monthly income of P 5,000 below, 45 out of 52 or 86 percent have the monthly payment of P 5,001 to P 10,000. While 1 out of 52 or 2 percent was family income every month ranges from P 10,000 to P 20,000, no family has a gain of P 20,001. As we can see from the data, most of it has the parent earning P 5,001- 10,000. We trace up the data of LatianE/S from the school year 2009-2010 that --2 out 50 or 4 percent have monthly income of P 5,000 below, 48 out of 50 or 48 percent have the monthly payment of P 5,001 to P 10,000. Nevertheless, there is no family earned from P 10,000 to P 20,000 and P 20,001. It stated that most of the family income every month ranged from P 5,001 to P 10 000. In the data of graduates of Latian Elementary School calendar year 2011 that one out 49 or 2 percent have monthly income of P 5,000 below, 48 out of 49 or 98 percent have the monthly income of P 5,001 to P 10,000. However, there is no result of the monthly payment of the family ranges from P 10,001 to P 20,000, and P 20,001 and majority of parents gets a low monthly fee of P 5,001-10,000. If we notice the data of respondents from Latian Elementary School from the school year 2011-2012 that 4 out 48 or 8 percent have monthly income of P 5,000 below, 42 out of 48 or 88 percent have the monthly income of P 5,001 to P 10,000, while 1 out of 50 or 2 percent income of family every month collected P 10,000 to P 20,000. It stated that most of the family income every month ranged from P 5,001 to P 10 000. Generally, the data found out that the graduates of Latian elementary school 2008-2012, majority of the parents had the low monthly income ranging (P5, 001-P10, 000).

Apao, Dayagbil&Abao (2014) mentioned that low-income earners usually face challenges accessing primary education. The children are too exposed to the intricacies and difficulty of earning a living where they are left with the only choice but to help their parents in daily work routines, which will hamper their attendance in school. Analyses show recurrent correlations of low attainment with specific ethnic minority groups, with Gender, and most strongly with low-income sections of society. It argues that reducing the proportion of children growing up in poverty will significantly raise average attainment levels than in-school factors (Dearing, Walsh, Sibley, Lee, John, Foley & Raczek, 2016; Parsons, 2016).

INDICATOS	YEAR									
	2007-2008		2008-2009		2009-2010		2010-2011		2011-2012	
	f	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	F	%
GENDER										
Female	26	54	23	44	23	46	24	49	23	48
Male	22	46	29	56	27	54	25	51	25	52
Total	48	100	52	100	50	100	49	100	48	100
NUMBER OF YEARS IN SCHOOLING										
Six years	45	94	49	94	48	96	47	96	48	100
Seven years	3	6.25	3	5.78	2	4	2	4	0	0
8 Years and above	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	48	100	52	100	50	100	49	100	48	100
ETHNICITY										
B'laan	36	75	33	63	29	58	31	63	30	62
Cebuano	11	23	19	36	20	40	18	36	16	33
Muslim	1	2	0	0	1	2	0	0	2	4
Total	48	100	52	100	50	100	49	100	48	100
EDUCATION OF PARENTS										
Elementary										
Undergraduate	33	69	34	65	24	48	25	51	20	42
Graduate	8	16	9	17	18	36	16	32	15	31
High School										
Undergraduae	4	8	6	11	5	10	5	10	5	10
Graduate	2	4	2	5	3	6	3	6	7	14
College										
Undergraduate	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Graduate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
Total	48	100	52	100	50	100	49	100	48	100
SIZE OF THE FAMILY										
Small	2	4	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	2
Medium	45	94	49	92	50	100	49	100	46	96
Large	1	2	2	4	0	0	0	0	1	2
Total	48	100	52	100	50	100	49	100	48	100
MONTHLY INCOME OF THE FAMILY										
Very Low (5,000 Below)	4	8	6	12	2	4	1	2	4	8
Low (5,001-10,000)	42	88	45	86	48	96	48	98	42	88
Average (10,001-20,000)	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	2
High (20,001 Up)	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
Total	48	100	52	100	50	100	49	100	48	100

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

G. Percentage of the batch 2008-2012 who graduated to secondary education

Table 2 focused on the percentage of Latian elementary school graduates from 2008-2012 who proceed to secondary in terms of their Gender. Using frequency represents a student that proceeds to secondary and graduates to secondary correspond to the percentage utilized in table 2.

The graduates of Latian Elementary School year 2007-2008 who proceed to secondary reveal that 10 out of 26 or 21 percent were female and 13 out of 22 or 27 percent were male. The majority of students who finished their secondary level were male. In 2009, 11 out of 23 or 21 percent mostly were female, and males got 31 percent or 16 out of 29. This

data is evidence that in the school year 2008-2009, majorities are males. We can have observed that in the school year 2009- 2010 graduates of Latian E/S that fulfill their secondary, 14 out of 23 or 20 percent were female and 15 out of 27 or 30 percent were male. In the school year 2010-2011, it could be noted that secondary graduates in this year spot that 18 out of 24 or 37 percent were female and 12 out of 25 or 25 percent were male. The school year 2011-2012, distinguish the data that among the graduates from Latian E/S which fulfill secondary, 15 out of 23 or 31 percent were female, and 19 out of 25 were male. Generally, majority of the graduates of Latian E/S who graduated to secondary from the school year 2008-2012 were male.

Moreover, the concept of free primary education has been around for some time; the UNESCO Institute of Statistics has still recorded a 1.1 percent illiteracy rate in the

Philippines. The Philippine Statistics Office also recorded that in 2015 only 68 percent of elementary school graduates proceeded to high school (Fuerte& Umali 2019).

INDICATOR	YEAR														
	2007-2008			2008-2009			2009-2010			2010-2011			2011-2012		
	Proceed to sec.	Grad. to sec.	%	Proceed to sec.	Grad. to sec.	%	Proceed to sec.	Grad. to sec.	%	Proceed to sec.	Grad. to sec.	%	Proceed to sec.	Grad. to sec.	%
Female	26	10	21	23	11	21	23	14	28	24	18	37	23	15	31
Male	22	13	27	29	16	31	27	15	30	25	12	25	25	19	39
Total	48	23	48	52	27	52	50	29	58	49	30	62	48	34	70

Table 2: Percentage of the batch 2008-2012 who graduated to secondary education

H. Common Reasons of Students of Not Proceeding to Graduate from Secondary Education

Table 3 present the common reasons for students not proceeding to graduate from secondary education. Frequency counts and percentages were utilized. The respondents asked common causes why they did not move to secondary. It revealed the following indicators; low income of the family who cannot support the education in secondary, responsibilities at home, illness, early marriage, and interest. It could be gleaned that during the 2007-2008 school year, 20 respondents stated the common reasons. Among them, 35 percent of pupils who did not pursue secondary education said their family income could no longer provide for them. Fifteen percent took responsibilities at home, while the distance of the schools hindered the 20 percent from their home, 10 percent of the pupils got an illness. Other 10 percent opted to get married early, and learners lost 10 percent interest in school. Moreover, in the school year 2008-2009, the table shows that there are 19 respondents. Among them, 26 percent said that their family could not support the education in secondary. Fifteen percent of them have responsibilities at home. Twenty-one percent said that distance is the hindrance that they could no longer proceed to secondary, 11 percent got sick and built their own family at a young age, and 16 percent lacked interest. Furthermore, graduates of Latian elementary school

in the calendar year 2010 told that the family's low income is still the factor where they did not enroll in secondary. It revealed that 42 percent out of 24 pupils had. At the same time, illness and early marriage got 4 percent of the total, and 20 percent are not interested in pursuing secondary education. In 2010-2011, low income was still one of the top reasons the pupils did not enroll in secondary. It signified 55 percent of them. Eighteen percent have responsibilities in their home. However, no pupils got an illness, but 9 percent got the same results: pupils got early marriage and lost interest. Finally, in 2011-2012 we could glean from the table that 38 percent of low-income families could not support their education in secondary and pupils take the responsibilities at home. Distance and illness got 12 percent. However, no pupil got early marriage and lost interest to pursue secondary level. Generally, in the table below, the common reasons why graduates of Latian E/S did not enroll in secondary are that most of them have low income and cannot support their secondary education level.

Moreover, less educated parents found in low-income conditions would contribute to the lower achievement levels of their children by the nature of their education or experiences (Hammond, 2015; West, 2007 cited by Renth, 2015; Renth, Buckley & Puchner 2015).

Common Reasons	2007-2008		2008-2009		2009-2010		2010-2011		2011-2012	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Low income of the family who cannot support the education in secondary	7	35	5	26	10	42	6	55	3	38
Responsibilities at Home	3	15	3	15	4	17	2	18	3	38
Distance	4	20	4	21	4	13	1	9	1	12
Illness	2	10	2	11	1	4	0	0	1	12
Early marriage	2	10	2	11	1	4	1	9	0	0
Interest	2	10	3	16	4	20	1	9	0	0
TOTAL	20	1000	19	100	24	100	11	100	8	100

Table 3: Common Reasons of Students of Not Proceeding to Graduate from Secondary Education

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data gathered, following conclusions are established:

- Majority of the graduates from 2008-2012 of Latian Elementary School were male, seven years in schooling, and B'laan. Their parents were elementary graduates, their family size is medium, and their monthly income is low, ranging from P 5,000.00 to P 10,000.00 monthly.
- Many of the graduates from 2008-2012 graduated to secondary. In 2007-2008, 23 out of 48 or 48 percent graduated to secondary. In 2008-2009 27 out of 57 or 52 percent, in 2009-2010 29 out of 50 or 58 percent, 2010-2011 30 out of 49 or 62 percent, and in 2011-2012 34 out of 48 or 70 percent graduated to secondary.
- The common reasons for students not proceeding to graduate from secondary education were family's low income, responsibilities at home, who cannot support education in secondary, and the distance from home to school.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Out of the results, it was recommended that:

- School may strengthen the parents mentoring program by conducting
- orientation on parents' duties and responsibilities to their children.
- School may initiate livelihood program by conducting orientation and top private sectors, local leaders to sponsor the program.
- School may recommend sponsoring agencies like Provincial and Municipal governments to support low-income families as recipients of the scholarship.
- Teachers will sponsor children of those low-income families by tapping the private sector and stakeholders.
- It is highly recommended that tulongsa mag-aaral program be implemented to address issues and problems on elementary graduates who cannot attend secondary education.

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